

SYNTHESIS MORPHOLOGY AND STRUCTURAL CHARACTERIZATION OF ZINC FERRITE NANOPARTICLES

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Abstract

Zinc ferrite ($ZnFe_2O_4$) nanoparticles were synthesized by sol-gel auto combustion method using citric acid as a fuel. The metal nitrate to fuel ratio was taken as 1:3. The as synthesized powder of Zn ferrite nanoparticles is annealed at $600^\circ C$ for 6 h and prepared sample was used for characterization and investigations of structural and magnetic properties. The structural characterization of Zn ferrite nanoparticles were done by X-ray diffraction technique. The crystallite size obtained by Scherer's formula is in the order of 29 nm. The lattice constant determined from XRD data is in the reported range 8.429 \AA . The morphological properties were investigated using scanning electron microscopy.

Keywords: Zn ferrite, Sol-gel auto-combustion, XRD, SEM, Garnet

Introduction

Ferrites are ferrimagnetic oxides consisting of ferric oxide and metal oxides. On the basis of crystal structure ferrites are grouped into three classes namely garnet, spinel and hexagonal ferrite. The spinel ferrites are widely studied because of their superior properties such as structural, magnetic, electrical and catalytic properties, all of which are different from those of their bulk counterparts and applications point of view in various and new fields like magnetic drug delivery, catalyst, sensors, biological, biomedical and medical science [1-4]. The spinel ferrite has the general formula of MFe_2O_4 where M is a divalent metal ion (Mn, Co, Ni, and Zn etc). Among spinel ferrites, Zinc ferrite ($ZnFe_2O_4$) has normal spinel structure and promising magnetic material for high-density recording applications because of their high magneto crystalline anisotropy, high coercivity, moderate saturation magnetization and high chemical and structural stability at higher temperatures, which make it a good candidate for the electronic components used in computers, recording devices, and magnetic cards [5-9]. The

properties of nanoparticles mostly depend on synthesis method therefore nowadays different synthesis methods are being used for synthesis nonmaterials. Zn-spinel ferrite nanoparticles have been synthesized using various methods, such as co-precipitation method, hydrothermal method, micro emulsion method, sol-gel method, sonochemical reaction method, ball milling, laser ablation and aerosol method [10-14]. Among synthesis methods, sol-gel auto combustion method has been used for synthesis of Zinc ferrite nanoparticles. Auto-combustion synthesis process is based upon the thermo-chemical concept used in the field of propellants and explosives, its extrapolation to the combustion synthesis of nano-oxides. A various fuels have been used in the combustion synthesis of ferrite nonmaterial, like glycine, urea, oxalyl-hydrazine, citric acid, and sucrose. All these fuels serve two purposes: (i) they are the source of C and H, the reducing elements, which form CO₂ and H₂O on combustion and liberate heat; and (ii) they form complexes with the metal ions facilitating homogeneous mixing of the cations in solution. The exothermicity of the redox reaction ranges from 1200 K to 1800 K. The nature of combustion differs from flaming to non-flaming depending upon which fuel used for preparation of nano-material. In the present work citric acid has been used to prepare Zinc ferrite nanoparticles. The present research report deals with the synthesise of zinc ferrite nanoparticles by sol-gel auto combustion method using citric acid as fuel and to investigate the structural and morphological properties of Zinc ferrite nanoparticles.

Experimental

Material and Synthesis

The ZnFe₂O₄ nanoparticles were synthesized by sol-gel auto-combustion method using citric acid as a fuel. The metal nitrates to fuel ratio was taken as 1:3. All the reagents used for the synthesis of Zinc ferrite nanoparticles were analytical grade and used as received without further purification. The stoichiometric proportion of Zinc nitrate Co(NO₃)₂ 6H₂O, ferric nitrate Fe(NO₃)₃ 9H₂O and citric acid C₆H₈O₇.H₂O were separately dissolved in minimum amount of distilled water using magnetic stirrer. After complete dissolution of metal nitrates in distilled water then Zinc nitrate and ferric nitrate solution were mixed and stirred sometime with constant heating at 90 °C. After some stirring citric acid solution was added to the nitrates solution. The all solution was again stirred for about 6 h at 90° Con a hot plate with continuous stirring until it becomes viscous and finally formed a very viscous gel. The temperature is

further raised up to 120⁰C so that the ignition of the gel suddenly starts. The dried gel was subsequently swelling into foam like and undergoes a strong self-propagating combustion reaction to give a loose Zinc ferrite nano-powder. Finally the as prepared loose Zinc ferrite powder was grinded for 30 min and annealed at 600⁰C temperature for 4 h in muffle furnace to improve the ordering and for further characterization.

Characterization

The crystalline phase of the prepared Zinc ferrite sample was identified by X-ray diffraction technique using XPERT-PRO system. X-ray powder diffractions were performed at room temperature using monochromatic Cu-K_α radiation with $\lambda=1.54060 \text{ \AA}$ operated at 40 kV and 35 mA with 2θ ranging from 20⁰ to 80⁰ at a step size 0.02⁰ per second. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) technique was used to study the surface morphology of the samples. Using SEM data grain size, specific surface area and morphology of the prepared Zinc ferrite nanoparticles were studied.

Results and Discussion

XRD analysis

Fig. 1 shows the XRD pattern of the annealed Zinc ferrite nanoparticles. The diffraction peaks observed at $2\theta= 30.32^{\circ}, 35.65^{\circ}, 43.33^{\circ}, 53.67^{\circ}, 57.24^{\circ}, 62.80^{\circ}$ corresponding to the (220), (311), (400), (422), (511) and (440) planes, respectively. In this XRD pattern other oxides or impurity phases are not detected therefore XRD patterns confirm the formation of cubic spinel type lattice of ZnFe₂O₄, which matches well with the standard XRD pattern. The lattice constant (a) of Zinc ferrite samples was obtained from the following equation.

$$a = d\sqrt{(h^2+k^2+l^2)} \quad \text{\AA} \quad (1)$$

Where, (h k l) are the Miller Indices, d is inter planner spacing. Thus, lattice constant was computed using the d value and the (h k l) parameters. The crystallite size (D) has been calculated from FWHM (full width at half maximum) of most intense peak (311) data using Debye-Scherrer's equation [15].

$$D = \frac{(0.9 \lambda)}{(\beta \cos\theta)} \text{ nm} \quad (2)$$

Where, D is the crystallite size, λ is the wavelength of Cu-K α (1.5405Å), β is the full width at half maxima of the most intense diffraction peaks and θ is the Bragg's angle. The reflection from (311) plane was used for determination of average crystallite size.

Fig.1. X-ray diffraction patterns of ZnFe₂O₄ nanoparticles

The volume (V) of the unit cell was calculated by using the following equation;

$$V = a^3 \text{ [Å]} \quad (3)$$

Where, V is the volume of unit cell, 'a' is the lattice constant. The X-Ray density (ρ_b) of the sample was calculated using the relation given by Smit and Wijn following formula [16].

$$\rho_b = \frac{8M}{N_A a^3} \text{ gm/cm}^3 \quad (4)$$

Where, M is the molecular weight and N_A is the Avogadro's number and 'a' is the lattice parameter. As there are 8 molecules in the unit cell, so 8 is included in the formula. The bulk density (ρ_m) of Zinc ferrite sample was determined using standard formula.

$$\rho_m = \frac{m}{\pi r^2 t} \text{ gm/cm}^3 \quad (5)$$

Where m is mass of pellets, r is the radius of pellets and t is thickness of pellet. Porosity (P %) of the $ZnFe_2O_4$ sample was calculated from X-ray density and bulk density.

$$P = \left(1 - \frac{\rho_m}{\rho_b} \right) \times 100 \% \quad (6)$$

Where, ρ_b is the X-ray density and ρ_m is the bulk density. The structural parameters such as lattice constant, unit cell volume, X-ray density, bulk density, porosity and specific surface area of Zinc ferrite nano particles are given in Table 1. From table 1, it was understood that the calculated values of lattice constant of Zinc ferrite nanoparticles is 8.378 Å which agree with the reported values [17]. The crystallite size of the Zinc ferrite nanoparticles is 26 nm. The X-ray density is found to be of the order of 5.301 gm/cm³. The bulk density of Zinc ferrite nano particles was measured from the standard formula [18].

The value of bulk density is of the order of 2.749 gm/cm³. It was observed that X-ray density of sample is greater than its bulk density. This was due to the pores present in the prepared materials. The percentage porosity (% P) was calculated from X-ray density and bulk density values. The porosity of Zinc ferrite nanoparticles is of the order of 32.14%, which is quite greater than that of bulk $ZnFe_2O_4$. The increase in porosity is due to preparation condition [19]. All the structural data of prepared Zinc ferrite nanoparticles is in the reported range.

Table.1. Lattice constant, volume of unit cell, X-ray density, bulk density, porosity and crystallite size from XRD data.

Structural Parameters	Values
Lattice constant (a)	8.378 Å
Volume of unit cell (V)	588.0 Å ³
X-Ray density (ρ_x)	5.301 g/cm ³
Bulk density (ρ_b)	2.749 g/cm ³
Porosity (p)	32.14 %
Crystallite Size(t)	26.00 nm

Scanning Electron Microscope Study

Fig.2. SEM images of ZnFe₂O₄ nanoparticles

Fig. 2 show morphological pattern of the prepared zinc spinel ferrite nanoparticles taken by scanning electron microscope (SEM). Evidently, from SEM images of the sintered zinc spinel ferrite samples it was seen that the morphology of the particles were almost spherical in shape, but agglomerated to some extent due to the interaction between magnetic nanoparticles. It can be observed that grains of uniform size are distributed throughout the surface [20]. The formation of nano size crystallites was confirmed through SEM images. The average grain size calculated from linear intercept method was found to be in nanometre range of 31 nm. The value of surface area is 81.62 for $ZnFe_2O_4$ spinel ferrite samples. Since the particle size decreases the surface area increases which indicate the nanocrystalline nature of the samples. It is well known that the crystallite size and surface area play an important role in the magnetic properties of ferrites due to the size of the magnetic domains.

Conclusions

Zinc ferrite nanoparticles of nano size have been synthesized successfully by sol-gel auto combustion method. X-ray diffraction pattern confirms the formation of cubic spinel structure in single phase without any impurity peak. The average crystallite size is obtained was of the order 26 nm. The lattice constant and other structural parameter are in the reported range. The average grain size determined from scanning electron microscopy technique is of the order of 31 nm.

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